

DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGY FOR ANTIANGINAL TABLETS USING DIRECT COMPRESSION METHOD

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Abstract: The data obtained on the study of technological and qualitative indicators of the antianginal tablets obtained by direct pressing are presented. The main criteria of the approach to the development of the composition and technology of antianginal tablets are briefly formulated.

Keywords: tablet, excipients, antianginal action, direct pressing method, technology

Tablets prepared by pressing are the most common type of tablets and are most often discs with a flat or biconvex surface. This shape ensures maximum strength of the tablet with minimal weight and optimal size, creates convenience in packaging, and facilitates swallowing. Tablets should have the correct shape, whole, without chipped edges. The technology of any preparation of tablets consists in the fact that the required amount of medicinal substance is mixed with the required amount of various excipients. Then pressing takes place on special tablet presses. Most of the active substances that are used in tablets do not have the properties that are needed for their direct pressing. This is isometric, that is, the correct shape of the crystals, good fluidity or flowability and necessarily good compressibility, low adhesion[1,4].

Direct pressing is performed only with the addition of additional substances, auxiliary substances that help to improve the properties of the active material for pressing. However, not all substances that have medicinal properties also have properties that make it possible to press. Other technologies for creating tablets are used for such substances [2,3].

Purpose: the purpose of this work was to create user-friendly, sufficiently bioavailable and stable combined dosage forms of antianginal action. This report presents the results of a study in the field of obtaining combined antianginal tablets by direct pressing.

Materials and methods: the analysis of the technological characteristics of the substance and excipients was carried out on devices from Erweka (Germany), the particle size was evaluated by microscopy using the Video Test program. For the development of tablets, we tested formulations with various compositions of excipients and their ratios. The main requirements for this group of excipients are: storage stability, good compressibility, the ability to quickly and completely release the active substance and form durable tablets. The analysis of the tablets was carried out according to the current regulatory documentation.

Results: obtained by direct pressing of antianginal tablets. The composition of the tablets includes, taking into account the physico-chemical and technological characteristics of the ingredients, auxiliary substances that ensure sufficient flowability of the tablet mass, its good compressibility and uniformity of filling the matrix of the tablet press, and hence the uniformity of the distribution of the active substance in the dosage form. The tablets obtained by the direct pressing method did not meet the requirements for tablet dosage forms. The results of the analyses obtained by studying the technological parameters of the ingredients showed the need for the addition of excipients that improve flowability. Various excipients recommended by the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Uzbekistan were used both individually and in combinations: lactose, glucose, microcrystalline cellulose, carboxy methylcellulose calcium carbonate, sucrose, corn starch, potato starch, magnesium stearate,

calcium stearate, stearic acid. But due to inappropriate technological properties, the tablets turned out to be of poor quality - the tablet mass stuck to the press tool, the tablets did not meet the requirements for disintegration and abrasion. The tablets obtained by direct pressing did not meet the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Uzbekistan for tablet preparations. Therefore, we decided to use the wet granulation method when tableting.

Conclusions: Thus, it is not possible to obtain antianginal tablets obtained by direct pressing, as a result of which it was determined to use the wet granulation method and the introduction of a complex of auxiliary substances into the composition.

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